

TRANSLATION

The Prophet (may God bless and assoil him!) has said "Whoever builds a mosque for God, God builds a palace as reward for him in Paradise."¹

During the reign of 'Alāu'd Dunya wad-Dīn Abu'l Muẓaffar Ḥusain Shāh, the Sultān—may God perpetuate his kingdom and majesty and exalt his authority and position!—this mosque was built by the great and honoured Malik, the exalted 'Aṭā Malik, may his high rank remain for ever! On the 25th of Rajab, 904 H. (1499 A. D.).

AN INSCRIPTION FROM RĀISEN FORT IN THE BHOPAL STATE.

By G. YAZDANI.

As in February, 1932, Mr. A. Marchive, Research Scholar, Department of Indian History, Allahabad University, wrote to the Director General of Archæology in India for a copy of this inscription, some inked rubbings of the record were prepared with the kind permission and help of the Bhopal State in whose jurisdiction Rāisen Fort is situated.² As the inscription has not been published before, I take this opportunity to edit its text with an English translation.

The fort of Rāisen is frequently mentioned in the annals of Malwa kings, and the mosque in which the inscripational tablet is set up has also some historic associations. In 934 H. (1528 A. D.), Bābur, after defeating Mednī Rā'i, repaired the mosque in Rāisen Fort, along with those at Chanderī, Sārangpur and Ranthambhor, which had been desecrated by the former being converted into cattle-sheds.³ In 938 H. (1531 A. D.), Bahādur Shāh of Gujarāt, after his conquest of Rāisen, appointed 'Ālam Kḥān as Governor of the place and had the *khutba* recited in his name at this mosque.⁴

The inscripational tablet measures 2 ft. 8 in. by 2 ft. 2 in., and is divided into thirty-six panels. Thirty-four of these are occupied by seventeen Persian couplets, and the remaining two by the praise of God, the Prophet and the king. The couplets are heavy in style and dull in sentiment and seem to be the work of a local poet. The style of calligraphy is *Naskh* of an ornamental type which has made the decipherment of the inscription somewhat difficult particularly at places where the stone of the inscripational tablet has weathered. The inscription records the building of a Jāmi' Masjid (Assembly Mosque) and a dome in 995 H. (1587 A. D.), during the reign of Akbar.⁵ I have deciphered the text as follows:—

Plate XI(b)

توحيد باري تبارک و تعالیٰ

و نعت محمد مصطفیٰ و مدح حضرت سلیمان

(۱) شکر مر حضرت الهی را کہ او دارد بقا

آفریدگار هر مهم (۶) مصطفیٰ و رهنما

¹ A well-known saying of the Prophet Muḥammad. See *Kanzu'l 'Ummal*, Hyderabad lithograph, Vol. IV, p. 139.

² Rāisen, 23° 20' N. and 77° 47' E., is the headquarters of a *Nizamat* in the Bhopal State. It is twelve miles from Salāmatpūr, a station on the G. I. P. Railway. There is bus service between Salāmatpūr and Rāisen.

³ *Briggs*, II, 60.

⁴ *Ibid.*, IV, 122 and *Zafaru'l Walih*, Vol. I, p. 263.

Malwa was conquered by Akbar in 1561 A. D.

(۲) ای توانا (۶) از همه قادر تویی آمرزگار

از لطف اگر خواهی گدا را تاج بخشی بی‌شمار

(۳) ای شه سلطان من جز تو ندارم تکیه گاه

بادشاهی را برانی سر گدا داری کلاه

(۴) زاهدانرا گر بخوای بر سر دوزخ نهدی

عاصیانرا هم توانی روضه جنت دهی

(۵) جمل عالم را پندای از تو خورام ای اله

بنده را گر بخوای کرم خرد دارن نگاه

(۶) کاف داشت

کاف حکمتی دیگر گذاشت

(۷) گر بخوای ای کریم تاج بر هر سر نهدی

زنده را جان ستانی مرده را جان دهی

(۸) در عهد سلطان السلاطین شاه سلطان ماست

شاه جهانگیر تاج سلیمان شاه ماست

(۹) صاحب این خرشید گنبد مسجد تو ر مدار

ملک رضی ابن ابراهیم مشهور مقطع نامدار

(۱۰) غانم الملک مخاطب شد ز حضرت شهنشاه

نام خرد در فلک از اله

(۱۱) ثانی الشمس قمر این مسجد گنبد نهاد

غانم الملک در عالم هر زمان باشی تو شاد

(۱۲) بیست الله است مسجد جامعی فرض نماز

و آن دگر فردوس عالم روضه خرشید ساز

(۱۳) غنچه گلزار اینک بین تماشای جهان

فرحت نما آرام دل جان هم نیاید دیدبان

(۱۴) من بعالم دید (۶) ... چند آئین که آرد دره ...

مثلش عمارتها نیامد گر نواز

(۱۵) مسجد محراب نادر ریخت گلهای نهال

خالق من کل شی قدرت از بر کمال

(۱۶) مهدی . . . زمان (۶) ثانی حق صدق داشت

اسم این مسجد و گنبد باغیخورد داشت

(۱۷) شد مرتب مسجد جامع ز فضل کردگار

بود تاریخ نهصد و خمس و تسعین در شمار

نقطه:

TRANSLATION

The praise (lit. unity) of the Holy and Most High God, the eulogy of Muḥammad the Chosen Prophet, and the encomium of His Majesty the Solomon-like king.

(1) Thanks unto Most High God, Who is ever-lasting and the creator of every effort (?), (the creator of Muḥammad) the Chosen and of every (other) leader.

(2) Thou art Almighty, Thou art Compassionate . . .
when Thou wilt Thou bestowest innumerable crowns on a beggar.

(3) O King of kings, I have no refuge except Thee: Thou mayest drive away a king and place the diadem on the head of a beggar.

(4) Thou mayest place the pious at the entrance of Hell; Thou mayest give the gardens of Paradise to the sinful.

(5) Thou art the refuge of the universe; I crave Thee O God; if Thou desirest, Thy benevolence protectest an humble being.

(6) *Kāf*¹ implied; *Kāf*
. added (?) further wisdom,

(7) O Benevolent, when Thou desirest Thou placest a crown on every head: Thou takest away the life from the living and bestowest life on the dead.

(8) During the reign of the king of kings, the monarch who is clad in the garment of a dervish: the world-conquering king, of the crown of Solomon, who is our lord.

¹ *Kāf* is the initial letter of the word *Kun* (meaning 'be') which God said when He created the universe.

- (9) The master (*i.e.*, the builder) of this Sun-like dome, the orb of the Pearl Mosque, is Malik Razī son of Chhajji the well-known fief-holder.
- (10) The emperor has bestowed upon him the title of Ghānimu'l Mulk (the Crusader of the State); . . . his name to heaven . . . by . . . God.
- (11) The Sun-like Qamar, Ghānimu'l Mulk, laid the foundation of this domed mosque; may both the worlds be joyful every moment . . .
- (12) This assembly mosque is the abode of God (Kā'ba) for the (performance of) compulsory prayers, and the other that is the garden laid out by Khurshid (Ghānimu'l Mulk) is the paradise of the world.
- (13) The flower-bud of this garden is such that thou mayest behold in it the show of the world, it will refresh thee, console thy heart and soul, and will not stare at thee.
- (14) In the world I have noticed . . . some laws (?) . . . but I have seen no building . . . like it.
- (15) The mosque with a beautiful arch, the floral designs of which have been wrought by a genius whose art shows perfection in every thing.
- (16) Mahdī . . . time . . . has given this mosque and the dome the appropriate name of Bāghi Khur (the Sun-gardens).
- (17) By the grace of God this assembly mosque was completed in 995 H. (1567 A. D.).

SOME PERSIAN INSCRIPTIONS OF THE PERIOD OF THE LODI AND MUGHAL SULTĀNS OF DELHI.

By MAULAWI SHAMSUDDIN AHMAD, M.A., INDIAN MUSEUM, CALCUTTA.

In the present paper I venture to study a few Persian inscriptions of the period of the Lodi and Mughal kings of Delhi. These form part of the Muslim Gallery of the Archæological Section of the Indian Museum.

No. 1

The first inscription to be dealt with is an epitaph of four lines in verse, each line being isolated between a pair of raised borders. It is carved on a spotted red stone measuring 3' 6½" × 1' 7½". The first and the third lines terminate each in a spirally wound twig with foliage at the end, while the second and the fourth rows are preceded by similar twigs but without foliage.

The slab was discovered while ploughing a field near a cemetery at Patiāli in the District of Etah, U. P., by a farmer, from whom Mr. Cotton, I.C.S., the Magistrate of the District, acquired it through Sayyid Aḥsan Shāh, a Tahsildar of Aligarh, and presented it to the Indian Museum in 1926. The stone has cracked vertically in the centre, being divided into two halves.

The epigraph is an elegy reminding casual visitors of the difference between the dead and the living, and imploring blessings from them when they happen to pass by the grave.

The style of writing is *Naskh* of clear and elegant execution; the curves and sweeps of the letters bear considerable affinity to those noticed in the inscription of Ibrāhīm Lodi¹ and other

¹ Blochmann, P. A. S. B., 1872, pp. 166-67.

(a) Inscription of Sultan Husain Shah of Bengal from Margram, Murshidabad District.

(b) Inscription from Raisen Fort, Bhopal State.

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